

ONLINE OBSERVATION AND SUPERVISION OF TEACHERS' INSTRUCTIONAL DELIVERY AND TEACHING PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 6 STUDENTS OF TAYABAS WESTERN ACADEMY

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ABSTRACT

The online class observation process is intended to assist faculty members in their teaching. In this time of pandemic teachers scrambled to create sustainable virtual spaces as education adapted to the pandemic. Online instruction will never be the same as in-person instruction, and there are many simple ways we can create virtual classrooms that inspire and accommodate all learners. The use of variety of educational platforms emerged that can be used during virtual classes. However, delivery of instructions must not suffer whether it is online or offline. The study aimed to determine the relationship of online observation and supervision of teachers' instructional delivery towards teaching performance. The respondents of the study were dominated by those twelve to thirteen (12-13) years of age with fifty-eight (58) and 53.4%, female with thirty-two (32) and 55.2%. The data indicate that the students perceived that online observation and supervision components in terms of related factors as classroom management (M=4.21%), student engagement (M=4.19), teaching pedagogy (M=4.24) and technological competence (M=4.30) were interpreted mostly as "often or madalas". Students perceived that teachers' instructional delivery and teaching performance in terms of curriculum and content (M=4.30), teachers' methodologies (M=4.23), classroom environment (M=4.21), and assessment and monitoring (M=4.23) were interpreted as "often or madalas" respectively. Online observation and supervision have no significant relationship towards teachers' instructional delivery and teaching performance. Online observation and supervision as to technological competence has significant relationship at the 0.01 level (2 tailed) towards teachers' instructional delivery and teaching performance as to curriculum and content. Since routines and drills help a lot during online discussion, teachers must utilize creative routines that will improve their teaching performance in managing online classroom. Since students have short attention span, teachers must engage them using different educational games that are now much more accessible in this New Normal. The study recommends that the teachers should provide more online assessment during virtual learning for the students monitor their own learnings. This is important because in this new normal, students sometimes learned by their own or with the help and guidance of their parents, guardians and teachers. It is also essential for them to know what to improve in their learnings. It is recommended that School administrator may consider planning, organizing, conducting seminars, training or workshops on how to cope with distance learning. Teachers should not stop learning different strategies and skills that will suitable to the level of intelligences and types of learnings of their students in the new normal. The future researchers may

develop programs for teachers and students on to improve of teachers' instructional delivery and teachers' performance.

Keywords: mode of learning, transactional distance learning, modular distance learning, online survey, online interview